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THE NEED TO IMPROVE THE SYSTEM OF TRAINING FUTURE HISTORY TEACHERS BASED ON THE HERMENEUTIC APPROACH

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Abstract: In this article, the effectiveness of future history teachers' knowledge development based on the hermeneutic-cognitive technology, hermeneutic-cognitive technology, and the hermeneutic approach is studied. Also, the hermeneutic approach and its importance in developing the knowledge of future history teachers about the laws of the historical process are analyzed.

Key words: history, historical process, legitimacy, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology, competence, hermeneutic, cognitive, technology, trend, technological, hermeneutic approach.

INTRODUCTION. Today, there are many issues remaining in the system of training future history teachers and in the teaching of history in higher education. These include the outdated approaches in history education, the inability to completely abandon the approaches inherited from the Soviet system, the limited ability to form new knowledge and skills due to the scarcity of modern research, the lack of a methodology aimed at developing a hermeneutic approach directed at distinguishing historical truths from falsehoods, and others.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. The issues of preparing future history teachers for professional activity, developing an understanding of historical processes, and enhancing historical communication are reflected in the scientific works of J. Anderson, D. Blazar, S. A. Henry, L. N. Aleksashina, V. V. Barabanov, P. A. Baranov, L. S. Baxmutova, Y. Y. Vyazemskiy, O. Y. Strelova, M. V. Korotkova, M. T. Studenikin, N. N. Lazukova, Y. M. Persanova, O. G'. Davlatov, A. F. Ismailov, Q. R. Shonazarov, B. X. Xodjayev, O. Musurmonova, M. Quronov, S. Nishonova, U. Mahkamov, E. Turdiqulov, R. Safarova, B. Adizov, A. Choriyev, Sh. Mardonov, D. Ro'ziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, and O. Jamoldinova.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The main goal of all knowledge gained through history has been to understand humanity and its essence, with the sciences of nature and spirit being products of these inquiries. Despite the achievements and discoveries made, the most complex and challenging issue in the 21st century remains the study of human thinking and understanding

processes. The philosophical hermeneutics of the past century also focused on understanding how the process unfolds and the factors influencing it.

All teachings, trends, and views emphasize that the main and most accurate way to reach truth is the idea being presented. In this sense, hermeneutics considers life's meaning and truth as the most appropriate form of knowledge, treating communication as a key process. In the course of communication, cultural, historical, and scientific values are created. According to hermeneutic thinkers, the primary task of philosophy is to find the meaning and essence of life in communication between people.

When discussing any event or phenomenon, it is crucial first to understand its essence as deeply as possible. Accepting everything we hear, see, and read without thoroughly thinking about it is a form of negligence. After all, what we hear may be incorrect, what we see may be false, and what we read may be far from the truth. Hermeneutic approaches, however, not only open up the holistic characteristics of understanding information, things, phenomena, and processes, but also examine both subjective and objective aspects.

The task of enriching the content of history education and activating students' cognitive activities opens up great opportunities for improving the forms and methods of teaching history. The content of history education becomes richer, existing forms and methods of teaching are improved, and new forms and methods emerge. The description of pedagogical processes is based on the laws of the educational process and its main stages (preparing students to perceive historical events, introducing the material, analyzing, generalizing, reinforcing, forming skills and competencies, and teaching students to apply acquired knowledge in practice). The form chosen depends on the content of the material at each stage of learning history.

The improvement of the future history teacher training system based on the hermeneutic approach has several key aspects that strengthen interest in studying past lessons. This is directly related to the complex process of understanding humanity's historical experience and the logic of life. The historical experience itself elevates the student's spiritual, educational, emotional, and practical comprehension of the social world to a new level. As a result, the student not only acquires knowledge but also forms perceptions of values. Knowledge and values related to understanding the past emerge through the observation and analysis of historical events and the drawing of necessary conclusions. Historical experience, and the conclusions drawn from historical processes, not only reflect the ready-made framework of knowledge and values

but also serve a moral function in the process of students' practical understanding of the world. This, in turn, develops qualities such as creativity and constructive attitude, which are essential for a democratic society. Historical experience serves as an inspiring and motivating tool for developing such qualities.

Reflecting on how famous thinkers from both the present and the past have interpreted the meaning and laws of historical processes, Cicero called history "the teacher of life," while Leonardo da Vinci believed that "to know the past and the history of world countries is the beauty of humanity and its intellectual product." The father of Russian history, N. M. Karamzin, wrote, "History is the sacred book of nations, reflecting their life and activities, showing the discoveries and moral values passed down by ancestors, serving as a mirror for interpreting the present and as a guide for the future." V. G. Belinsky emphasized that "to understand the present and have an indication of the future, we must inquire into the past." V. O. Klyuchevsky stated, "By studying our ancestors, we understand ourselves. Without knowing history, we cannot clearly comprehend why and for what purpose we came into this world, and what we strive for."

In this regard, we should focus on terms that reflect hermeneutic approaches when interpreting the meaning of history and explaining the laws of historical processes.

Understanding is the process of comprehending the meaning of historical reality and creating it, which does not fall within the subject-object boundaries of historical knowledge, but leads to the need for understanding. Understanding is a more complex process than knowing, in which the information obtained is linked with the past, present, and future of thinking. Understanding is part of the research field of various social sciences. It is worth noting that understanding is the main category of hermeneutic methodology, as evidenced by the recognition of "the art of understanding" in hermeneutics.

Hermeneutic understanding, unlike social understanding, focuses on grasping the author's initial intent behind the text. In our view, understanding is the art of receiving signs conveyed through actions from one consciousness to another. Scholars who view understanding as part of the ontological process regard it as the assimilation of new knowledge and a component of existing consciousness. Other definitions also describe understanding as an intellectual-psychological process that expresses the feelings of an object or another person within reality.

The next term, often contrasted with understanding by most authors, is explanation.

Explanation – The logical-methodological explanation of the essence of a historical event, phenomenon, or action. Explanation is carried out in cooperation (with the participation of the person explaining and the person receiving the explanation) in individual, triological, and polylogical forms. Nowadays, the issue of explanation has been raised to the level of a special research problem in historical science and is being studied by specialists. In particular, modern epistemology focuses on scientific explanation. In this context, explanation must primarily meet two requirements: 1) adequacy – the argument-based (descriptive) representation of the explanation must be directly related to the phenomenon, event, reality, or action being explained; 2) direct or indirect correlation.

In the framework of the hermeneutic approach, improving the system of training future history teachers requires their ability to engage in dialogue with historical periods. When interacting with historical reality, students seek answers to questions such as: “Why did this situation arise?”, “What were the reasons for the emergence of this process?”, “How could the development of historical events have been changed?”, “If I were a participant in that reality, what would I have done?”, “How could I have helped the people in this situation?” and others.

Studying world history and analyzing the history of humanity enriches the student's understanding of human nature and broadens their conclusions about human activity and potential. Through studying humanity's history and the history of their ancestors, students explore the world, expand their conceptions about it, and can draw concrete conclusions. In this process, the educational significance of history becomes particularly evident.

According to the hermeneutic approach, explanation can only be tied to the past and present, as it interprets past or current phenomena. Despite research, there are several challenges in historical explanation: 1) the diverse social and cultural characteristics of the objects, their varying periods of occurrence, and the differing types and norms of rationality; 2) the impossibility of fully rationalizing human behavior (actions). Therefore, when explaining historical processes, it is appropriate to apply methods and approaches in harmony rather than in isolation.

Alongside understanding and explanation, interpretation also holds significant importance in hermeneutics. Interpretation (from the Latin

"interpretatio" – explanation, clarification) is a cognitive process aimed at understanding the essence of concepts or elements through their material forms and embellishments. The problem of interpretation is one of the fundamental issues in epistemology, methodology of science, logic, philosophy of language, semiotics, and other fields, with special significance in philosophical hermeneutics. Today, in addition to the humanities, interpretation is also used in natural sciences as a material verification of the compatibility between scientific theory and ontological reality. A single event may have multiple theoretical interpretations, and interpretation enables comparison across different scientific theories.

In the logical domain, interpretation is the process that supports the structure of logical constructs. In social and humanitarian fields, interpretation expresses the verbal structure of concepts. The methodological development of interpretation in the humanities can be outlined as follows: 1) interpretation as a field of knowledge focused on the study of artistic allegories and classical heritage in ancient culture; 2) interpretation as a field that expresses the meaning of symbols in religious texts, the basis of medieval Christian culture – exegesis; 3) interpretation as a primary issue of philosophical hermeneutics, studying understanding and the creation of meaning.

Improving the system of training future history teachers based on the hermeneutic approach requires addressing the following educational, developmental, and formative tasks:

- Cultivating historicity: enabling students to understand and evaluate past and present events in relation to one another, fostering creative thinking, striving for scientific objectivity, evaluating historical ideals across the nation and the world, and encouraging independent conclusions based on studying historical sources.
- Developing the ability to understand historical issues: enabling students to assess historical figures and events with a moral perspective.
- Educating future citizens who are aware of the histories and cultures of different nations, respect other cultures, and understand the progressive importance of cross-cultural relations, thus promoting intercultural dialogue and respect for others.

Conclusion: The classification of history lessons and the use of their diverse types is not based on the teacher's personal preference but is instead derived from the necessity to successfully implement the educational and developmental tasks of history education in higher education. It is also tied to

the fundamental laws of history education. Therefore, when choosing the type of lesson, the teacher must consider the ideological content and character of the subject, as well as ensure that students understand and assimilate the material in accordance with the new laws of the educational process. Selecting the lesson type in this way helps to successfully implement the educational and developmental tasks of history education in higher education and assists in creatively solving issues related to teaching methods and approaches.

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